

Determination of molecular weight of neutral amino acids with chloramine-T

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A simple titrimetric method for the determination of molecular weight of neutral amino acids is described. The method involves the addition of chloramine-T to amino acids in water followed by determination of unreacted chloramine-T by iodometry.

Although various methods are reported in the literature for the determination of α -amino acids¹, few are commonly used. The important colorimetric reagents for the determination of α -amino acids include ninhydrin², 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde³ and *o*-diacetylbenzene⁴. Recently, we have successfully used chloramine-T for the determination of iodine value of different oils as well as for many synthetic purposes⁵. This prompted us to devise an operationally simple titrimetric method for the determination of neutral α -amino acids and the results are presented here.

Results and Discussion

Molecular weights of various amino acids were determined in six trials and are given in Table 1. As a typical comparison, the molecular weights were determined by the formal titration method, which requires a series of steps⁶. The standard deviation for all the sample were less than 1% of the respective molecular weight.

In a typical experiment, a known excess of standard solution of chloramine-T is added to a known amount of aqueous amino acid. After the reaction is complete, unreacted chloramine-T is determined by iodometry. By carrying out a blank experiment simultaneously, the amount

of chloramine-T consumed is determined. As the overall reactions require one mole of chloramine-T per molecule of amino acid, which is equivalent to one mole of iodine, the molecular weight (*M*) of the amino acid is determined by using the equation,

$$M = \frac{W \times 2000}{12 \times (V_1 - V_2) \times N}$$

where, *W* is the weight of amino acid in 60 ml of the reaction mixture (mg), *V*₁ the volume of thiosulfate solution required for the blank, *V*₂ the volume of thiosulfate solution required for the actual experiment and *N* the normality of thiosulfate solution.

The proposed method makes use of the fact that α -amino acids are known to undergo oxidative deamination and decarboxylation by chloramine-T to yield an aldehyde containing one carbon less than the parent amino acids⁷ involving one molecule of chloramine-T per molecule of amino acids. A detailed reaction mechanism is shown in Scheme 1.

Experimental

All the reagents were of analytical reagent grade. Dis-

Table 1. Molecular weight of amino acids

Amino acid/ (Mol. wt)	Time min	Experimental values*						Average	Std. dev.
		1	2	3	4	5	6		
Glycine (75)	240	74.70 (18.20)	75.30 (18.60)	75.16 (18.80)	74.80 (20.40)	75.30 (17.80)	75.10 (18.40)	75.06	0.25
Alanine (89)	30	89.26 (20.20)	88.94 (24.80)	88.77 (22.40)	89.22 (22.80)	89.15 (30.00)	88.90 (20.80)	89.03	0.22
Valine (117)	30	116.82 (26.80)	117.34 (32.20)	117.07 (31.80)	116.80 (41.60)	116.95 (31.80)	117.15 (38.20)	117.02	0.21
Leucine (131)	30	130.94 (32.40)	131.20 (27.80)	131.70 (35.00)	130.80 (34.00)	130.64 (35.60)	131.35 (30.06)	131.05	0.39
Tryptophan (204)	30	204.22 (27.70)	204.10 (28.00)	203.80 (22.60)	203.89 (33.00)	204.50 (18.80)	203.56 (24.30)	204.01	0.33
Threonine (119)	30	119.36 (33.00)	119.34 (27.80)	118.80 (24.80)	118.92 (15.40)	119.36 (14.80)	119.12 (30.20)	119.15	0.25
Tyrosine (181)	30	180.80 (44.60)	181.06 (21.50)	181.25 (24.20)	180.89 (21.00)	181.32 (17.80)	180.75 (26.20)	181.01	0.24

*Value in paranthesis indicates the weight of amino acid taken in mg.

Scheme 1

tilled water was used throughout. Glycine, alanine, valine, leucine, tryptophan, threonine and tyrosine were used. A 0.01 M amino acids and 0.01 M chloramine-T solutions were prepared in distilled water (tryptophan and tyrosine in hot water).

Procedure : A mixture of a 0.01 M amino acid (20 ml) and a 0.01 M chloramine-T (40 ml) solutions taken in an Erlenmeyer flask was set aside at room temperature for 30 min (4 h for glycine). A blank was run simultaneously. To an aliquot (5 ml) of the reaction mixture were added 10%

KI solution (1 ml), water (2 ml) and 2 N sulphuric acid (1 ml) and the liberated iodine was titrated with standard sodium thiosulfate solution (0.01 N) using starch as indicator. From the difference in the volume of sodium thiosulfate solutions consumed, the molecular weight was calculated.

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